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De: The Lancet Team <em@editorialmanager.com>
Para: Manuel Graña <manuel.grana@ehu.eus>
Asunto: Your Submission THELANCET-D-23-00184

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Title: Recovering trust in the vaccines

Dear Prof Graña,

Thank you for submitting your Letter to *The Lancet*. Having discussed your Letter with the Editor-in-Chief, and weighing it up against other submissions we have under consideration, I am sorry to say that we are unable to accept it for publication. Please be assured that your Letter has been carefully read and discussed by the Editors. Thank you for your interest in *The Lancet*, I hope this decision does not deter you from considering us again in the future.

Yours sincerely

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